

Exploring start-up scene: Polish founders across globe

Survey

Section 1: General Information

1. **Country of Operation:**
2. **Role/Position:**
3. **Nationality:**

Section 2: Startup Information

4. What sector does your startup operate in?
 - Biotech
 - Medtech
 - Deep Tech
 - Other (please specify)
5. Year of Establishment:
6. Number of Employees:
7. Stage of Development:
 - Idea/Concept
 - Early Stage
 - Growth Stage
 - Established
8. Funding Status:
 - Bootstrapped
 - Seed Funding
 - Series A
 - Series B and beyond
 - Other (please specify)

Section 3: Contributions and Impact

11. What inspired you to start your company?
12. What are the key innovations or technologies your startup is developing?
13. How do you perceive the impact of your startup on the industry?
 - High Impact
 - Moderate Impact
 - Low Impact

- Not Sure
14. Can you share any notable achievements or milestones your startup has reached?

Section 4: Challenges and Opportunities

15. What are the main challenges you face as a founder in your sector?
- Funding
 - Talent Acquisition
 - Regulatory Hurdles
 - Market Access
 - Other (please specify)
16. How do you address these challenges?
17. What opportunities do you see for growth and expansion in your sector?
18. Do you feel that being a Polish founder has influenced your startup journey? If so, how?
19. What support or resources would be most beneficial to you as a founder?
- Mentorship
 - Networking Opportunities
 - Access to Funding
 - Regulatory Guidance
 - Other (please specify)

Section 5: Policy and Ecosystem

20. How would you rate the support from local and national governments for startups in your sector?
- Excellent
 - Good
 - Fair
 - Poor
21. What policy changes or initiatives would you recommend to better support startups in your sector?
22. How do you perceive the global startup ecosystem in your sector?
- Highly Supportive
 - Moderately Supportive
 - Neutral
 - Unsupportive
23. What are the key differences you have noticed between the startup ecosystems in Poland and other countries?
24. Would you be willing to participate in a follow-up interview?
- Yes (provide e-mail address)
 - No

Section 6: Additional Comments

- 25. Please share any additional comments or insights you have regarding the biotech, medtech, and deep tech startup ecosystems, particularly in relation to Polish founders.**

Section 7: Demographic information

1. Age
 - a. Under 25
 - b. 25-34
 - c. 35-44
 - d. 45-55
 - e. 55-64
 - f. 65 and above
2. Gender
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. non-binary/third gender
 - d. Prefer not to say
3. Highest level of education
 - a. High school diploma or equivalent
 - b. Bachelor's degree
 - c. Master's degree
 - d. Doctorate (PhD)
 - e. Other (please specify)
4. Field of study
 - a. Life sciences
 - b. Engineering
 - c. Computer science
 - d. Business
 - e. Arts and humanities
 - f. Social sciences
 - g. Other (please specify)
5. Years of experience in the industry (Please specify).....
6. Country of your highest level of education